

TA'LIM VA KO'ZI OJIZLAR

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10060812>

Annotatsiya. Ko'rlarning barmoqlari bilan o'qish orqali o'rganishi mumkinligini qadrladi va u o'z shogirdlariga o'rgatish uchun ko'tarilgan alifbo tizimini ishlab chiqdi.

Kalit so'z: ko'zi ojizlar, ta'lim haqida, tarixi, ko'zi ojizlar tashkiloti.

ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ И СЛЕПЫЕ

Аннотация. Он понял, что слепые могут научиться читать пальцами, и разработал систему рельефного алфавита для обучения своих учеников.

Ключевые слова: слепые, об образовании, история, организация слепых.

EDUCATION AND THE BLIND

Abstract. Appreciated that the blind could learn by reading with their fingers, and he developed a raised alphabet system to teach his students.

Key words: blind people, about education, history, organization of blind people.

Fransuz faylasufi Denis Didro o'zining "ko'zi ojizlar va ta'lim haqida muhim muhokamani o'z ichiga olgan birinchi risolalardan birini yozgan. Ko'ra oladiganlar foydalanish uchun ko'rlarga maktub" (1749). Inshoda teginish tuyg'usini ko'r odamlarda o'qish uchun yaxshilash mumkin, bu 19-asrda Brayl yozuv tizimining ixtirosini bashorat qiladi. Didro Sonderson haqidagi bo'limni o'z ichiga oladi va insonning yutuqlarida hissiy tajribaning rolini ta'kidlab, ko'rish qobiliyati tushunish va fikr yuritish qobiliyatining markaziy qismi emas degan fikrni yoqladi. Didroning ko'rlar falsafasiga yana bir ta'siri Parij musiqasi hissi edi Melanie de Salignac musiqasi o'qish va do'stlar bilan yozishmalar uchun teginish shaklini yaratgan. Didro de Salignacni mumkin bo'lgan narsaning namunasi sifatida ko'rdi va u ko'rlarni ko'rish qobiliyatining etishmasligiga emas, balki o'qituvchi ko'rning qanday ko'nikmalarga ega ekanligiga e'tibor qaratsa, ko'rlar ta'lim olishlari mumkinligini ta'kidladi. Didro frantsuz ma'rifatining eng nufuzli faylasuflaridan biri sifatida ko'rlarni tarbiyalash uchun falsafiy asos yaratdi.

1784 yilda frantsuz xattotlik professori Valentin Xauy Parijda birinchi ko'zi ojizlar maktabini ochdi. Xayuga 1770-yillarda karlar uchun birinchi davlat maktabini ochgan abbé de l'Epee Charlz-Mishel ta'sir ko'rsatdi. Xauy iste'dodli ko'r avstriyalik pianinotchidan ilhomlangan. Mariya Tereziya fon Paradis. Fon Paradis Xauyga o'zi ishlab chiqqan, o'qish va yozish uchun ishlatiladigan teginish alifbosini ko'rsatdi. Fon Paradis Iogann-Lyudvig Vayssenburg ismli ko'zi ojiz nemis odami bilan xat yozgan va u o'z navbatida boshqa ko'zi ojiz talabalarga ikkalasi bir-biriga yozish uchun ishlatgan barmoq alifbosini o'rgatgan. Hay ko'rlarning barmoqlari bilan o'qish orqali o'rganishi mumkinligini qadrladi va u o'z shogirdlariga o'rgatish uchun ko'tarilgan alifbo tizimini ishlab chiqdi. Xauy usullari keyingi yarim asr davomida ko'rlar o'qituvchilari tomonidan qabul qilingan modelga aylanadi. Ko'tarilgan rim harflarini o'qish unchalik samarasiz edi va Xauy ko'rlar uchun nima ishlayotganiga qiziqqandek, ko'rlar uchun jozibali ko'rinadigan tizimni xohlardi.

Ko'zi ojiz o'qituvchilarning ta'kidlashicha, ko'rlar uchun zarur bo'lgan narsalar va ko'rlarning o'zlarini ta'kidlagan narsalar haqiqatan ham ishlaganligi o'rtasidagi ziddiyat keyingi ikki asrda ko'rlarning markaziy tashkilotchi kuchiga aylandi. 19-asr boshlariga kelib, Angliyada bir

qancha maktablar, jumladan, Liverpool (1791), Edinburg (1793), Bristol (1793) da paydo bo'ldi. Bu maktablar ingliz savdo maktabi modellari bo'yicha ishlab chiqilgan bo'lib, u yerda o'quvchilarga o'qish va yozishdan ko'ra hunar o'rgatilgan. Iogan Vilgelm Klayn 1804 yilda Vena shahrida ko'zi ojizlar maktabiga asos solgan. Ko'rish qobiliyatiga ega tengdoshlari bilan sinfga kirishdi. Ushbu uchta model - Xaüy, ingliz savdo maktablari va Venadagi Klein - keyingi asrda ko'r bolalar nimani o'rganishi kerakligi haqida munozaralarga sabab bo'ldi. Ba'zi o'qituvchilar ko'zi ojizlar kattalardek o'zlarini boqishlari uchun hunar o'rgatish yaxshiroq deb hisoblashsa, boshqalari klassik ta'lim ko'rlarni hurmatli kasblarga undaydi, shuningdek, inson qobiliyatining imkoniyatlariga misollar keltirishini ta'kidladilar.

XVII-XVIII asrlarda ma'rifatparvar faylasuflar o'rtasida ko'rlar tushunishning tabiati to'g'risida munozaraga sabab bo'lganidek, 19-asr ijtimoiy islohotchilari ham ko'rlarni qay darajada "reabilitatsiya qilish" yoki kengroq dunyoda o'z o'rnini egallashga o'rgatish mumkinligi haqida bahslashdilar. jamiyat hissa qo'shadigan fuqarolar sifatida. Amerikalik pedagog Semyuel Gridli Xou, 1831 yilda Bostonda Nyu-England ko'zi ojizlar ta'limi institutini ochgan (keyinchalik nomi bilan atalgan). Perkins Ko'zi ojizlar maktabi) - Qo'shma Shtatlardagi ikkinchi maktab - ko'rlarni dunyoda o'z yo'lini topib, jamiyatning mustaqil a'zosi bo'lish uchun o'qitish va o'qitish mumkin, deb ta'kidladi.

Xou maktabi butun Qo'shma Shtatlardagi maktablar uchun namuna bo'ldi. Qisman Xouning muvaffaqiyati uning mashhur shogirdlaridan olingan. Laura Bridgman, kar va ko'r qiz, 1837 yilda Xou maktabiga o'qishga kirdi. Xou har kim o'qish va yozishni o'rganishi mumkinligini isbotlamochi bo'ldi va u Bridgman tilini barmoq imlosi va ko'tarilgan yozuv orqali o'rgatishni boshladi. Bridgman oxir-oqibat barmoq imlosi va yozma so'z bilan muloqot qilish mahorati uchun milliy va xalqaro miqyosda shuhrat qozondi.

Keyinchalik Qo'shma Shtatlarda tashkil etilgan ko'zi ojizlar uchun maktablarning aksariyati davlat tomonidan moliyalashtirildi, bu ko'zi ojizlar uchun xayriya korxonasi sifatidagi ta'limdan soliq dollarlari bilan to'lanadigan huquqqa o'zgarganini anglatadi. Ko'zi ojiz bolalar XX asrgacha ko'r bolalardan tashqari turar-joy maktablarida ta'lim olishda davom etdilar. 1920-yillarga kelib o'qituvchilar va ko'zi ojizlar himoyachilari ko'zi ojizlar o'z tengdoshlari bilan maktabga borishlari kerakligi haqida zo'rlik bilan bahslash boshladilar. 1970 yilga kelib, bu g'oya asosiy oqim deb nomlanuvchi harakat uchun asos bo'ldi. ning o'tishi bilan 1975 yilda "Barcha nogiron bolalar uchun ta'lim to'g'risida" gi qonunning asoschisi 1990 yildagi Nogironligi bo'lgan shaxslarni ta'lim to'g'risidagi qonun (IDEA)), ko'zi ojiz bolalarni asosiy oqimga aylantirish huquqqa aylandi. Ko'zi ojizlar maktablarining ahamiyati kamayib, ko'zi ojizlar bilan ko'rlarning integratsiyalashuviga aylandi.

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